

of thiourea and also some substituted thiourea as according to the equation :

(R = H, CH₂ = CH - CH₂-, C₆H₅).

The mechanism proposed by us for this reaction is based on the stoichiometry of the reaction which is 1:1 and identification of the reaction products. The reaction has been utilized for the milligram determination of thiourea and its derivatives using potassium iodide and starch as indicator. The results of these determinations are within one per cent of the theoretical value (Table I).

We have also found that formic acid is oxidized

by N-bromosuccinimide in acid medium at room temperature :

The reaction is quantitative and has been utilized for the milligram determination of formic acid⁶ within accuracy of $\pm 1\%$.

As a brominating reagent in substitution reactions :

Tiwari, Sharma and Shukla⁷ have employed N-bromosuccinimide for the bromination of aromatic

TABLE I⁵. DETERMINATION OF SOME THIOUREAS

Amounts taken (mg)	Thiourea		Phenylthiourea		Allylthiourea	
	Recovery (mg)	Error %	Recovery (mg)	Error %	Recovery (mg)	Error %
1 2	2.0069	+0.34	2.0011	+0.05	1.9907	-0.46
2 3	2.9890	-0.37	3.0017	+0.06	2.9978	-0.07
3 4	4.0138	+0.34	4.0300	+0.75	4.0040	+0.10
4 5	4.9859	-0.28	5.0410	+0.82	5.0050	+0.10

amines and phenols in acid medium. The reaction is quick, quantitative and proceeds as follows :

TABLE II⁷. DETERMINATION OF AROMATIC AMINES AND PHENOLS

Sample	Amount taken (mg)	Equivalent NBS*	Recovery (mg)	Rrror %
1. Aniline	2.50	3	2.45	-1.8
2. m-Nitroaniline	3.00	2	2.91	-3.0
3. o-Nitroaniline	2.52	2	2.46	-2.4
4. o-Toluidine	3.00	2	3.10	+3.3
5. Sulphanilic acid	4.00	3	3.80	-5.0
6. p-Aminobenzoic acid	3.22	3	3.16	-1.9
7. m-Aminobenzoic Acid	3.12	3	3.09	-1.0
8. o-Aminobenzoic acid	2.50	3	2.43	-2.8
9. Diphenylamine	2.00	6	1.87	-6.5
10. Phenol	2.00	3	2.03	+1.5
11. o-Nitrophenol	2.12	2	2.08	-1.9
12. p-Nitrophenol	1.90	2	1.86	-2.1
13. m-Nitrophenol	2.22	2	2.15	-3.2
14. p-Chlorophenol	1.56	2	1.49	-4.5
15. o-Hydroxybenzoic acid	1.85	3	1.77	-4.3
16. m-Hydroxybenzoic acid	1.65	3	1.61	-2.4
17. p-Hydroxybenzoic acid	1.90	3	1.88	-1.1
18. Resorcinol	2.12	3	2.13	+0.5
19. α-Naphthol	2.00	2	2.05	+2.5
20. β-Naphthol	2.10	1	2.00	-4.8

*NBS = N-bromosuccinimide.

The reaction forms the basis of a method for the quantitative determination of aromatic amines and phenols in milligram quantities⁷ (Table II).

tion of coloured compounds e.g. nitrophenols and nitroanilines. The presence of carboxylic and sulphonic acid groups in the nucleus considerably retards the speed of the reaction which may be explained by assuming that the reaction proceeds in two steps :

The method is specially suited for the determina-

The reaction in step (i) is fast while in step (ii), it is comparatively slow.

The number of bromine atoms entering the amine or phenol may be determined by the stoichiometry of the reaction in each case. The determinations have been carried out by back titrating the reagent which gives better results than by direct titration.

As a brominating reagent in addition reactions :

N-bromosuccinimide has also been used as brominating reagent for allyl alcohol, allyl amine, crotonic acid and diallyl⁸ in which the addition of bromine takes place at the double bond. This reaction has also been used for the determination of the iodine number of fats and oils⁹.

The reaction of N-bromosuccinimide on alkenes in polar medium (acetic acid) has been studied in our laboratory. The stoichiometry of the reaction has been found to be 1:2 in substrate versus N-bromosuc-

cinimide for monoalkenes. In case of compounds containing more than one isolated double bonds, the stoichiometry changes accordingly and each of the π -electron centre takes up two atoms of bromine.

This reaction has been utilized for the micro-determination of olefinic double bonds¹⁰. The determinations have been carried out in 2-10 mg sample range in acetic acid medium. The reaction time in most cases is 10 minutes after which excess of the reagent is back titrated iodometrically. The percentage recovery of the C=C is within $\pm 2\%$ of the theoretical value (Table III).

Addition to conjugated dienes :

Under similar experimental conditions the reaction between 1:3 conjugated dienes and N-bromosuccinimide has also been studied. The reactions with sorbic acid, phenyl butadiene carboxylic acid, 1:4 diphenyl butadiene and muconic acid have been thoroughly investigated and applied for their quantitative

TABLE III¹⁰. DETERMINATION OF UNSATURATION IN MONOALKENES

Sample	Amount taken (mg)	% C=C calculated	% C=C recovered	Error %
1. Stilbene	4.10	13.33	13.23	-0.10
2. Crotonic acid	5.40	27.90	29.74	+1.84
3. Cinnamaldehyde	7.11	18.17	17.20	-0.97
4. Crotonaldehyde	3.295	34.27	34.44	-0.17
5. Cyclohexene	6.200	29.21	27.12	-2.09
6. Vinyl acetate	2.100	27.90	29.80	+1.90
7. Mesityl oxide	3.730	24.45	23.18	-1.27

TABLE IV¹⁰. DETERMINATION OF UNSATURATION IN CONJUGATED DIENES

Sample	Amount taken (mg)	% C=C calculated	% C=C recovered	Error %
1. Sorbic acid	4.50	42.85	41.90	-0.95
2. Phenyl butadiene carboxylic acid	5.30	27.58	28.55	+0.97
3. 1:4 Diphenyl butadiene	5.40	23.24	23.75	+0.51

determinations. The stoichiometry of the reaction has been found to be 2:1 in N-bromosuccinimide and dienes.

The reaction, in case of 1:4-diphenyl butadiene, proceeds smoothly at room temperature and time is about ten minutes. But in case of sorbic acid and phenyl butadiene carboxylic acid, the reaction mixture requires slight heating before accurate results are obtained. However, no reaction took place in the case of muconic acid and it could not be determined. This may be explained by the fact that the presence of two electron withdrawing carboxylic groups at the end carbons of the conjugated system makes the reaction extremely slow. For the same reason sorbic acid and phenyl butadiene carboxylic acid, each of which has only one carboxylic function at one end, show slow reactivity and reaction mixture is required to be heated. The conjugated dienes add bromine to 1:4 positions which is a common mode of addition in such compounds.

However, it can be inferred that in these reactions N-bromosuccinimide has been found to behave as other brominating reagents like bromine monochloride and potassium bromate bromide mixture in acid medium.

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